

THE ISSUES ON INCREASING STUDENTS MOTIVATION ON TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Talipova Nilufar Abduvasikovna,

*English teacher of the national institute of Pop Art after named B.Zakirov
at the state Conservatory of Uzbekistan*

Abstract: Motivation both external and internal is a main factor of successful students at all stages of their education, namely acquiring knowledge and academic achievements. Besides these, in teacher- led lesson, it can play a pivotal role in providing and supporting that motivation in classroom students. Motivated teacher is decisive to prosperous and successful classroom, since they look at edifying through different spectacles, in doing so these pedagogues motivate their students. It assists to galvanize, guide and uphold positive behavior a period of time.

Keywords: Continuous easement, teacher guidance, teacher-led lessons, autonomous learning, specify objectives, friendly spirit of competition, self learning environment.

Аннотация: Мотивация, как внутренняя так и внешняя, является основным фактором успешности учащихся на всех этапах их обучения, именно приобретение знаний и академический достижений. Помимо этого на уроках под руководством учителя, он может сыграть ключевую роль в обеспечении и поддержке этой мотивации у школьников. Мотивированный учитель имеет решающее значения для процветающей и успешной учебной аудитории, поскольку они смотрят на назидание с разных сторон, при этом эти педагоги мотивируют своих учеников. Это помогает гальванизировать, направлять и поддерживать позитивные поведение в течение определённого периода времени.

It is clearly seen that, it takes time and a lot of effort to investigate whole classroom learners morals and position of studying as all students are not motivated similarly or equally. According to the facts, educators gained all tutorial knowledge and well-educated have sometimes lack of skills to keep students on track. So whether you are a new and unexperienced tutor, seek to advantage some teaching techniques to motivate your students and to encourage them to satisfy their true potential. And here is some simple tips to ameliorate. Students motivation.

Give students self-managment. During the continuous assessments, teacher guidance is essential to keeping kids in order to nurture their abilities by motivating and allowing to have some choices and opportunities while doing some tasks and types of assessments quierer or which challenges to work on can give them a sense of control. It is possible, this method can be the best way of hold them involved and engaged.

Specify the objectives. At the beginning of the year define clear objectives, rules, norms, bonuses and expectations of students. This leads to no confusion and students go toward on their target-related paths. Since it can be so rustrating to finish a task completely or even, to behave that it should be eisted and sett off objectives.

Change your scenery: Classroom is great and main place of learning for student, but sometimes it seems so dull that sitting in front of desk day in and day out is too monotonous. Regenerate new classroom atmosphere and renew intrigue in subject metters or just learning in general for their backgrounds. Give students a chance for being out of classroom that Organize field trips to do do some experiments or make research, even head to the library and bring speakers, lectures or some authors who can influence them. Brain loves novelty and innovations as a new settings to stay keeping them motivated and nurtured.

Offer various experiences: Not all students will respond to lesson in the autonomous method, for some practical students hands on experience can be the best some of them love reading book in a quite place, some of them like group work. How will you solve this problem? Just mix up lesson in order to keep whole

classroom motivated. So students focus on the things they like best with different preferences. Doing so will assist them stay engaged and more attentive with all elements.

Use positive competition: In some cases, competition can motivate learners to try harder and feel self-confident cause competition is not always bad thing that sometimes pupils feel some panic if they find challenge to catch up or not to be winner. Therefore, operate friendly spirit of competition in your class. Competition can be other opportunity for students to show their knowledge while group games.

Be excited: One of the best ways is to get students motivated is to share your enthusiasm. Cause when you are appreciate about teaching, they will be much more excited about learning. This is simple.

Know your students: If you get to know your students this is more than just memorizing their names of students should know their teacher has a genuine interest in them and cares about them and their academic achievements are also essential. This phenomenon creates a safe learning environment and inspire them to work hard when they appreciate as they want to get rewards, praise and good feedback from someone who they respect them as individuals.

Give praise when earned: Even as adults we supplicate recognition and praise, and students at any age are no exception. Scholars can give learners a bounty of motivation by rewarding academic achievements in public, giving praises for a job well done and sharing work as an example.

Make things fun: Students who see school as a place where they can have a fun will be more motivated and inspired to pay attention and do the work that is demanded them than those who regard it as a chore. Setting off new intriguing activities into your school syllabus can assist learners who struggle to stay attracted and make the classroom a much more friendly area for all students.

Track progress: It can be a bit challengable to see just how far they have come, namely with subjects that a difficult for them. Tracking can come in handy in the classroom not only for students but also for teachers. Teachers can use this

method to encourage students by show them visually what they gain and how much they are learning.

Offer rewards: Everyone loves rewards, bonuses and incentives, so offer your students the chance to gain them that it is an excellent supplement of motivation. Events like watching movies, pizza parties, karaoke and even something as simple as sticker on a paper make students work on themselves during target related period. Consider your students nature and personalities according to their needs to determine appropriate rewards for your class.

Motivation can be main factor of learning process at the all stages of education that it should be created high spiritual environment. So, avoid being teacher who is really dull to be master of profession and to obtain high learning process by keeping your students growing level. To use following tactics is effective to improve students motivation.

Reference

1. Bonwell, C, C ; Eison J A (1991) Active Learning: Creating Excitement in the classroom.
2. Duckworth A.L, Quinn P. D, Lynam D R, Leober R; Southamer-Leober, M (2001), Role of test motivation in Intelligence Testing
3. Gottfried A E (1990) Academic Intrincic motivation in young elementary school children. Journal of Educational Psychology
4. Keller, J M (2010) Motivational Design for Learning and Performance. The ARC Model Approach, Springer Science + Businesses Media, LLC
5. Pintrich P R, De Groot E (1990), Motivational and self regulated learning components of classroom academic performance. Journal of Educational Psychology, 82.